

Reproducibility of Deep Learning Experiments

Jeaneth Machicao
Universidade de São Paulo
machicao@usp.br

Ali Ben Abbes
FRB-CESAB
ali.benabbes@fondationbiodiversite.fr

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We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the land and sea in all nations. We honour their profound connections to land, water, biodiversity and culture and pay our respects to their Elders past, present and emerging.

Model: a typical research pipeline

Writer

Reporting on their experiment and wants to achieve **reproducibility** of their work

peer review

Reader/Reviewer

reads a **paper** out of interest and wants to **check** the **validity** or quality of an experiment.

Machicao, J., *et al.* 2022. Mitigation Strategies to Improve Reproducibility of Poverty Estimations From Remote Sensing Images Using Deep Learning. *Earth and Space Science* 9. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022EA002379>

Reproducer/Replicator

reproducing/replicating an **experiment** either in whole or in part.

Have you ever tried and failed to reproduce another scientist's experiments?

Is your DL experiment reproducible?

Can you reproduce a reported DL experiment?

peer review

difficulties in reproducing **computational** experiments

**Reproducibility
in modern
science is a
challenge!**

Reproducibility issues in numbers...

Researchers are...

Unsuccessful

in reproducing third-party experiments [1]

Unable

to reproduce their own research material [1]

Reluctant to share

code, data or both [2]

[1] Baker, M. (2016). 1, 500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility. *Nature*, 533(7604), 452–454. <https://doi.org/10.1038/533452a>

[2] Harris, Jenine K.; Johnson, Kimberly J.; Carothers, Bobbi J.; Combs, Todd B.; Luke, Douglas A.; Wang, Xiaoyan (2018). "Use of reproducible research practices in public health: A survey of public health analysts". *PLOS ONE*. 13 (9): e0202447.

24,11% were
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~800K
Python
notebooks

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Python
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4.03% produced the **same results**

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Of those who **failed** produced the same results

50% got **different results** for more than **half** of notebook cells.”

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Distribution of Jupyter cell reproducibility

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Some terms...

Reproducibility: regenerate **results** using **original data, software, and parameters**

Some terms...

Reproducibility: regenerate **results** using **original data, software, and parameters**

Replicability: arrive at the **same results** using **new data**

**Reproducibility of
Deep Learning
experiments is even
more challenge!**

Experiments using DL remain **difficult**
to reproduce due to the **complexity** of
the techniques used ^[1-4].

[1] Pineau, J., Vincent-Lamarre, P., Sinha, K., Larivière, V., Beygelzimer, A., d'Alché-Buc, F., et al. (2020). Improving reproducibility in Machine Learning research (A report from the Neurips 2019 reproducibility program). ArXiv Retrieved from <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.12206>

[2] Renard, F., Guedria, S., Palma, N. D., & Vuillerme, N. (2020). Variability and reproducibility in deep learning for medical image segmentation. Scientific Reports, 10(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-69920-0>

[3] McDermott, M. B. A., Wang, S., Marinsek, N., Ranganath, R., Foschini, L., & Ghassemi, M. (2021). Reproducibility in machine learning for health research: Still a ways to go. Science Translational Medicine, 13(586). <https://doi.org/10.1126/scitranslmed.abb1655>

[4] Heil, B. J., Hoffman, M. M., Markowetz, F., Lee, S.-I., Greene, C. S., & Hicks, S. C. (2021). Reproducibility standards for machine learning in the life sciences. Nature Methods, 18(10), 1132–1135. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01256-7>

Besides ...

... there are other difficulties in reproducing DL experiments

a small

variation in

may lead
to different
results

● DATASET

● OPTIMIZATION

● HYPERPARAMETERS

● DL ARCHITECTURES

● INFRASTRUCTURE

How can you save yourself time and wasted effort?

Can you reproduce a reported DL experiment?

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peer review

This

**and recommended actions can
make this possible!**

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Earth and Space Science

Research Article |

Mitigation Strategies to Improve Reproducibility of Poverty Estimations From Remote Sensing Images Using Deep Learning

J. Machicao, A. Ben Abbes, L. Meneguzzi, P. L. P. Corrêa , A. Specht, R. David, G. Subsol, D. Vellenich, R. Devillers, S. Stall, N. Mouquet, M. Chaumont, L. Berti-Equille, D. Mouillot

First published: 06 August 2022 | <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022EA002379>

If you are a **Writer** or a **Reader/Reviewer**

peer review

use this
**Reproducibility
checklist**

- ✓ The description of the dataset
- ✓ FAIR sub-principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability)
- ✓ The description of the DL architecture and hyper-parameter optimization process
- ✓ The infrastructure and implementation
- ✓ Reported experimental results and theoretical claim
- ✓ The shared code

If you are **reproducing** or **replicating** a **DL experiment**

Use our recommendations for the most frequent issues with:

Quality of the Dataset

DL Experiment

Implementation and
Infrastructure

FAIR Principles

If you are **reproducing** or **replicating** a **DL experiment**

Use our recommendations for the most frequent issues with:

Quality of the Dataset

DL Experiment

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FAIR Principles

- **Validate** the **data** set used in the study
- Use a **sample** of the **dataset**
- **Check parameters** of the datasets or code.
- **Check** the **preprocessing** steps.
- **Verify** the **data construction** method.
- **Test** different **configurations** of **data split**.

If you are **reproducing** or **replicating** a **DL experiment**

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FAIR Principles

-
- A teal curved arrow pointing from the "DL Experiment" box to the list of recommendations.
- Look for **workflows**.
 - Look for **model architecture** as source code.
 - Look for **different setups** of experiments.

If you are **reproducing** or **replicating** a **DL experiment**

Use our recommendations for the most frequent issues with:

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DL Experiment

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FAIR Principles

-
- A teal arrow points from the "Implementation and Infrastructure" box to the list of issues.
- **Internet** flaws.
 - **Bugs**.
 - **Versioning**.
 - Source code is available but there are **many branches**.
 - **Programming language**.

If you are **reproducing** or **replicating** a **DL experiment**

Use our recommendations for the most frequent issues with:

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DL Experiment

Implementation and Infrastructure

FAIR Principles

- Some **FAIR** principles are **mandatory** in **dataset design**.
- Some **FAIR** principles **need scientific community agreement** and information about dataset quality.
- **Accept uncertainty** when achieving **FAIR**, because a dataset is never perfect.

An illustration of a person in a dark suit standing on a wooden plank that extends from the left edge of the frame. The person is looking towards a large, dark mountain in the distance. At the peak of the mountain, a red flag is flying on a tall pole. The background is a light blue sky, and the foreground is a white, cloud-like base. The overall scene is a metaphor for reaching a goal or a destination.

**Take home
message!**

Improve reproducibility!

A **gold** standard in modern science is to **achieve full replicability** of scientific experiments or, *when not possible*, **achieving reproducibility** (Peng, 2011).

...thus ensures **open** and **accessible**
research, which accelerates the
progress of the **scientific community**.

**CREATE!
REPLICATE!
IMPROVE
REPRODUCIBILITY!**

Inter-University Research Institute Corporation
National Institutes for the Humanities
**Research Institute for
Humanity and Nature**

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OF QUEENSLAND
AUSTRALIA**

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Thankyou

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